

Civil Service Reforms in Kazakhstan and Its Influence on Modernization

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Abstract : Civil service (public administration) is an important social institution of society properties. Civil service institution had a significant impact on modernization processes in Kazakhstan through ensuring the functioning of all the subsystems of social life. This article is an attempt to analyses the reforms of public service institution in Kazakhstan and to assess its influence on modernization processes.

Keywords : civil service, Kazakhstan, modernization, a national model of civil service, civil service reforms, bureaucracy

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